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TEACHING GRAMMAR IN CONTEXT: CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES FOR HIGH SCHOOL LANGUAGE LEARNERS

Shukurullayeva Ozodaxon Baxrom qizi,

3rd year student of Uzbekistan State World Languages,
English philology faculty, Tashkent

***Abstract.** This article explores challenges and opportunities, proposing strategies for effective teaching grammar in context. It discusses how to use instruction in teaching past simple by implementing an interview about a historical documentary since the method makes grammar more relevant and engaging and provides students with a practical and culturally significant language module.*

***Keywords.** Grammar in context, task-based learning, authentic materials, real-life context, goal-oriented task, communicative language teaching, contextualized grammar learning, cognitive approach, grammar instruction.*

Introduction. Grammar instruction has long been a cornerstone of foreign language education, traditionally taught through isolated rules and exercises. However, as language acquisition theories have evolved, educators have increasingly recognized the importance of teaching grammar in context - where grammatical structures are embedded within meaningful, real-life communication. This shift aligns with communicative language teaching (CLT) principles, which emphasize the integration of language form, meaning, and use. For high school foreign language educators, this approach presents both significant challenges and

exciting opportunities.

Methods for Teaching Grammar in Context in High School Foreign Language Education and its methods collectively address the challenges of balancing grammar instruction with communicative fluency, ensuring that students not only learn the rules but can also apply them meaningfully in authentic situations. (Ellis, R.)

1. Task-Based Learning (TBL). Task-based learning is an effective method for teaching grammar in context, as it focuses on using language to complete meaningful tasks rather than on isolated grammar drills. In this approach, students are given real-world tasks, such as planning a trip, conducting an interview, or solving a problem, which require the use of specific grammatical structures. Teachers design activities that allow students to naturally apply grammar rules while engaging in communicative tasks. This method not only reinforces grammar in context but also promotes critical thinking and collaboration. By using language in practical situations, students develop fluency and gain a deeper understanding of how grammar functions in everyday communication. (Nation, P., & Newton, J.)

2. Authentic Materials and Real-Life Contexts. Using authentic materials—such as newspaper articles, videos, advertisements, songs, and social media posts—allows students to see grammar used naturally in real-world contexts. Teachers can select materials that align with specific grammar points, giving students exposure to language as it is actually used by native speakers. *For example*, a lesson focusing on past tense verbs might incorporate an authentic interview or a historical documentary. This method not only makes grammar more relevant and engaging but also provides students with a model of language that is both practical and culturally significant.

Results. Methods - Task-based Learning and Authentic Materials demonstrate positive outcomes in terms of grammar retention, student engagement, and overall language proficiency. Each approach addresses the need for

contextualized grammar learning, making grammar instruction more relevant, engaging, and effective for high school foreign language learners.

1. Task-Based Learning (TBL): Improved Grammar Retention and Application. Task-based learning has shown significant improvements in students' ability to retain and apply grammar structures effectively. By engaging in meaningful, goal-oriented tasks, students naturally internalize grammar rules, as they must use them to complete the task successfully. (Nunan, D.)

Research indicates that students who participated in TBL activities demonstrated better long-term retention of grammatical forms compared to those who learned grammar through traditional rote memorisation exercises. The use of grammar in practical, communicative settings allows students to see the functional application of grammar, which helps them understand its relevance in real-life situations. TBL's focus on practical tasks rather than abstract grammar exercises leads to increased student motivation.

Authentic Materials and Real-Life Contexts: Enhanced Understanding of Grammar in Context. The use of authentic materials significantly improves students' understanding of how grammar functions in real-world contexts. Authentic texts expose students to a wide range of grammatical structures used by native speakers, providing examples that are relevant and culturally significant. This immersion in real-world language use helps students understand not just how grammar works, but why certain structures are used in particular situations. (Richards, J. C., & Rodgers, T. S.).

To sum up, what had been said, it should be concluded that teaching grammar in context offers a promising approach to foreign language education in high schools, addressing the need for more engaging and effective learning environments. The use of authentic materials - texts and media created for native speakers, such as news articles, podcasts, films, and advertisements - provides students with exposure to language as it is truly used in everyday life.

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THE CONCEPT OF SOCIOCULTURAL COMPETENCE

Shukurullayeva Sarvinoz

Student of Uzbekistan State World Languages University,

English Philology faculty

Email: shukurullayevasarvinoz9@gmail.com

Abstract. *Sociocultural competence is a critical aspect of effective communication in a globalized world. This article explores the multidimensional nature of sociocultural competence, emphasizing its cognitive, behavioral, emotional, and social components. The discussion highlights the significance of integrating sociocultural insights into educational practices, particularly in foreign language teaching. The development of sociocultural competence is framed as a dynamic, lifelong process that requires continuous learning and adaptation to diverse cultural contexts. By fostering empathy, cultural self-awareness, and appropriate behavioral responses, individuals can navigate cross-cultural interactions with sensitivity and effectiveness. The article concludes by underscoring the importance of pedagogical strategies that promote sociocultural competence in educational settings.*

Keywords. *Sociocultural competence, intercultural communication, cultural*